

TRAIN THE TRAINER

A digital resource to guide you in planning and conducting your own Train the Trainer workshop

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ABOUT EU-CITIZEN.SCIENCE

The EU-Citizen.Science project is building the central platform for citizen science in Europe. It will be a place to share useful resources about citizen science, including tools and guidelines, best practices and training modules. This will make citizen science knowledge created in Europe accessible to all and enable people to initiate their own activities. It will also enable anyone involved with or interested in citizen science to learn more and get involved.

ABOUT THIS RESOURCE

This resource aims to support citizen scientists in conducting a Train the Trainer workshop. The methodology within this resource details the critical components and considerations necessary and will aid practitioners in having the confidence and understanding to employ this training technique. This guidance is aimed primarily at contributory citizen science projects, and provides advice mainly to those who wish to host face-to-face training. Many of the principles can also be adapted to suit online trainings and the concept can be utilised for trainings across a broad range of subject areas.

WHAT IS TRAIN THE TRAINER?

Train the Trainer (TTT) is a learning method that equips people with the skills and understanding of a project, in order to deliver training, programmes or projects to others. In this context, a project partner from a citizen science project trains people to be “facilitators” – these facilitators will then train other people (participants) in how to contribute to the citizen science project.

TTT provides an understanding of the focus area, familiarity with delivering the content of the project and practical coaching and facilitation skills. Importantly, to maintain bidirectional information and knowledge flow, facilitators should have the opportunity to provide feedback that can influence protocols and should be encouraged to contribute and participate in multiple aspects of the project. The aim of Train the Trainer is to build the knowledge, skills and understanding required to successfully run the training element of a project, allowing project partners to effectively pass on the training to others.

Certain competencies should be proliferated to all participants, particularly in citizen science, and so sufficient training is critical. Train the Trainer ensures that participants are doing the same science, with the same rigour and level of understanding, sharing best practise amongst the network and training in a safe and engaging way. Ensuring that everyone has the correct skills and knowledge to participate in the project promotes more effective and accurate data collection. Equipping others with the skills and knowledge to train audiences is cost-effective, intelligent and efficient.

TRAINING DESIGN

DESIGNING THE TRAINING IS THE FIRST STEP. THE SCOPE AND ENGAGEMENT PATHWAY WILL FEED IN TO THE DECISION MAKING AROUND FACILITATORS AND THE LEARNING CONTENT.

RESOURCE

Train the Trainer will cost time and money – it is crucial to ensure you have sufficient resources to run a course through to completion. This includes time planning the course content, people to train the facilitators, remaining in contact and communications and resource provision. Resources will also be needed for recruitment – it should be established who is responsible for recruiting the facilitators and to ensure ample material is supplied to support this process.

SCOPE

The vast opportunity that citizen science presents poses challenges for administration and operation of projects and activities. When considering a Train the Trainer approach, it is important to consider the scope of your project and whether it aligns with this methodology. The scope of a project will have direct implications for the delivery schedule, the facilitators employed, the monitoring and review and the learning aspect. The following questions should be reviewed when considering a TTT approach.

COLLABORATION

Are you collaborating? Co-facilitating? Lecturing? This should be established prior to delivering the Train the Trainer. Different projects will thrive under different working styles. The structure of the sessions and the level of interaction and, more importantly, input that facilitators have in the sessions is important to consider, as it will ultimately shape the learning content. It is important to allow facilitator input, providing ample opportunity for the to feedback and shape the nature of the training and the project.

TIME SCALE

The timescale of your project will ultimately influence whether TTT is the right method or not. While courses can be as short as 1-2 days, there is a considerable amount of pre and post course commitment that is necessary. This should be considered when designing the projects life cycle and deciding whether or not to conduct a TTT course. You should also consider the complexity of your data collection method; a complicated methodology will require time and experience, so if you have a short project time scale, you may wish to consider a different training strategy. Basic skills and knowledge are transferable in short sessions, but a deeper understanding and opportunity to learn a broader skill set requires lengthier training. You should consider your timeline extensively, considering restrictions (such as monitoring seasonal events or working outdoors in the best possible conditions) and allocating time for training.

COMMUNICATION

Communication is key with TTT. Projects must liaise with their facilitators consistently, supporting them with delivering training and updating them on the progress of the project. Similarly, it is important to establish communication channels between both project designers and facilitators, and the participants, to ensure they feel confident and comfortable with their skills and understanding moving forwards.

Communications are often conducted on an ad-hoc basis, and is rarely detailed thoroughly as part of the programme design. Owing to the commitment in time and cost, it is imperative that communications before, during and after the project are considered and planned.

GEOGRAPHIC SCOPE

One of the benefits of TTT is that it allows citizen scientists across a broad geographic scale to be trained effectively. However, limits to this do exist; for instance, if you are a team based in the UK but you want global data, you will incur a cost in training facilitators and then sending them across the globe to deliver the training to citizen scientists. You should, therefore, consider the scope and scale of your project and whether it is feasible to reach this using TTT.

INTEGRITY

Train the Trainer relies on facilitators remembering and regurgitating the information provided to them. There has been question as to the authenticity and integrity of this approach, in that information may be relayed incorrectly or with less gravitas than intended, meaning that the people being trained may not uphold the integrity of the survey technique or information being detailed.

PROJECT TYPE AND AUDIENCE

TTT equips people with the skills and knowledge needed to be effective facilitators. Therefore, it is important to consider who your target participant is. This will determine the suitability of TTT for your project – different stakeholders and audiences will have different needs and requirements, as well as varying levels of understanding about a topic. If you are working with people who are already experts in the field, a workshop of this nature may be unnecessary. Members of the public may lack the skills required for data collection, while policy makers or scientists may have limited understanding of communications and volunteer management. Audiences can be composed from a range of backgrounds and ages, and have diverse motivations for participating. It is important to consider the relevance of the project to your target audience and communicate this with them clearly, enabling them to invest and commit to participation. You should consider that, depending on audience, you may need to adapt training to accommodate different cultural and social requirements, particularly when working across different countries and settings (e.g. schools, businesses etc.).

Additionally, the necessity of training will vary depending upon the type of project. For example, a project with a very simple methodology or method of data collection may not require this extent of training. For example, a project that uses an identification app such as SEEK by iNaturalist is less likely to need to train participants in ID skills. Why do you need to run a TTT? Asking 'why do we need to run a train the Trainer' will establish the necessity of it to your project. Assessing why you desire or require a TTT course is important for establishing aims and objectives. Clear aims will guide the course content and enable facilitators to understand the purpose of the course and the aims that they need to pass on to wider audiences. It is impossible to know if objectives have been met if they aren't clearly established in the first instance.

ENGAGEMENT PATHWAY

The engagement pathway details the journey that people go on through the duration of the Train the Trainer. While there should be a pathway for the project as a whole, there should be a specific pathway for the Train the Trainer aspect of the work, detailing recruitment, retention, participation and resignation. The checklist below details considerations to make when mapping your pathway of engagement -

- What is the time-line of the project and the TTT?
- What are the desired outcomes and objectives of the project and the TTT?
- How will engagement with facilitators be funded and where will it take place (e.g. venue and location)?
- How many times will you meet with facilitators and how many times will they deliver the project to wider audiences?
- What will be your communications plan?
- Will time be given to establish benefits and barriers of participation and map out their potential effects?
- Is participation in the project enjoyable?
- How will facilitators be recruited?
- How will you ensure facilitators have the correct skills needed? Will time be allocated to practise the citizen science activity, including demonstration and survey method?
- How will the purpose of facilitators be considered and communicated?
- Will facilitators be offered opportunities to contribute in the wider context of the project?
- How will you establish a shared language and clear expectations from one another?
- How will participation in the project be rewarded and recognised?
- How will you evaluate and monitor the process? How will you keep in touch throughout and after the process? How will you gather feedback?
- What is your exit strategy - Will there be future opportunities? Will contact continue? How will you communicate developments and results of the project?

FACILITATORS

Prior to recruitment, considerations should be made to ways of working and target audiences. Protocols should be in place to ensure the chosen facilitators are right for the role, and the role is right for them. This includes -

Values and ethics – Having a clear policy or framework that project partners, facilitators and participants agree to will increase the accountability and establish ways of working. Similarly, you should make legal considerations regarding data protection and health & safety.

Communication channels – establish how you will communicate with and support your facilitators and ensure it is clear who reports to who. This includes the responsibility of reporting between participants and project teams/facilitators.

Data processing – who is responsible for processing the data gathered by participants and what are time requirements for this?

Why should they participate – who is your target audience and why is your project a good fit for them? This will help to streamline recruitment and increase the likelihood of accessing audiences who want to contribute.

What are your requirements – what is the expected time commitment, what are your expectations, how will you be inclusive and promote diversity and what are some of the key skills you would like your facilitators to have and/or learn?

Level of participation – consider whether you will operate a top-down or bottom-up approach to facilitation and whether facilitators will be involved in multiple stages of the project, such as design or dissemination, sampling strategy and methods. This is critical to ensure bidirectional information flow.

Engagement – establish boundaries and a framework of engagement. Points of contact and regular communication channels are imperative and it should be clear who the responsibility falls upon for managing facilitators and participants. Safeguarding protocols should be detailed and rigorous, considering social, emotional, mental and pastoral components.

Facilitators are often volunteers, but can also be people affiliated with the project or project partners. There is often an aspect of recruitment in order to acquire enough facilitators to meet the demands of the project.

When recruiting, and if resources allow it, it is useful to hold interviews for facilitators, particularly on larger projects or projects with lots of interest. This will help you to establish more about the person, what their strengths and expertise are, what support they may need to conduct the role and what their motivation is. Addressing these questions will help in assessing the suitability of the person to the role and vice versa and whether they align with the target audience and can support the aims of the project.

When recruiting, it is crucial to be clear about the requirements of the project and assess the capacity of the person to adhere to this. Address your expectations and consider theirs; transparency and clarity avoids confusion and ensures objectives are met. Use this stage as an opportunity to learn more about the facilitators. Ultimately, they are contributing a unique set of expertise; whether it be scientific knowledge, administration skills or learning experience, each facilitator has something to offer, and it is important to understand and acknowledge what their strengths are.

Once facilitators are recruited, it is important to sustain the professional relationship. Retention of facilitators is imperative to the continued dissemination of knowledge and uptake of participants. It is important to consider how you will support facilitators in their work, providing professional development, resources and continued training to reflect updates in the project. Ensure you have outlined support for volunteers when considering time and funding allocations. Enforce the ways of working surrounding inclusivity, diversity and ethics, embracing the varying skills and knowledge that facilitators will provide. Recognise contributions to the project, rewarding and citing them wherever possible, and provide facilitators with opportunities to get involved in the wider scope of the project, should they wish. Consistent monitoring is important – gather feedback from your facilitators and their participants about the training and the project methodology. Adapt in response to concerns. Following the project's completion, or the end of the data collection period, ensure you review the process. Provide facilitators with feedback form, assess what was done well and what was more challenging. Ensure that feedback is acknowledge, considered and utilised in the project.

LEARNING CONTENT

The relevance of many of the aspects listed will vary depending upon the subject matter and the context, time scale and resource availability of the project. You can adjust the time spent on each section depending on the importance to the project. Similarly, the structure and content of the learning will be heavily influenced by time and resource availability.

1 – 3-day training

Introduction & Purpose of the training

An introduction to what citizen science is

The project and its scientific background

Subject knowledge

Data collection methodology, including time to practise

Facilitation skills – presenting, ideas sharing, challenges and opportunities,

Listening skills

Volunteer Management – recruiting, communications

3 + day training

Everything included in a 1 – 3-day training

Extended practise of the data collection method

Facilitation skills (extended) – learning styles, group dynamics, posing questions, designing your own training

Volunteer management (extended) – team building

You may wish to establish pre-training work for your facilitators. This is beneficial in setting the context for their role and can be useful if time is limited during the training. This could include preparing a short presentation, reviewing the learning materials you will be using or reviewing a project website and thinking of some questions they have. This can be useful in providing clarity about the project and the training, ensuring all involved are clear about the aims and objectives of the project.

Introduction

Begin by welcoming everyone and conducting introductions. Allow time for each facilitator to tell the group a bit about themselves and why they have decided to get involved. This serves the purpose of reviewing the expectations of participants, whilst also demonstrating to them that this is an important component to include when they are facilitating. Tell the group a bit about the project partners; who they are, their background and expertise and the general motive for participating. General housekeeping should be discussed (i.e. fire alarms, exits etc.) and you should run through the schedule of the workshop.

Purpose of the training

It is important to clarify the aims of the day – set the context for why the training is happening. Relate this to local and global interests, establishing the relevance of the project to the facilitators and the wider public. Describe what the aims of the TTT session are and what facilitators will take away from the workshop.

An introduction to what citizen science is

Clearly defining citizen science is important in setting the context for the training. Facilitators with a limited understanding of citizen science will benefit from learning more about its history, opportunities, collaborations and audiences, allowing them to understand the context of the project and training. Here, you could introduce the benefits of citizen science to scientific research.

The project and its scientific background

Present the project and its scientific background, offering an understanding of the projects context and rationale. Project aims should be clearly defined and accompanied with information about how the facilitators will help to achieve these goals. You should also outline the protocols that facilitators will need to adhere to. Discussing the scientific background of the project will help to establish a local and global context for why the project is happening. This helps to establish the connection between the project and the motivations of the facilitators. Establish who the contributors to the project are and offer information on the opportunities for participation. If your project exists within a platform, introduce it, particularly if it is utilised for communication or data submission. Take time to answer questions and address any concerns. Finish by detailing the specific objectives of the Train the Trainer.

Subject knowledge

A key component of the learning session will include delivering background knowledge to your project. This assigns context to the research and equips facilitators with the understanding and knowledge to inform participants and answer questions. The level of subject knowledge you want to deliver will vary based upon the requirements of your survey method – identifying the key metadata will allow you to establish the key information necessary to deliver. It is important to take regular breaks for facilitators to ask questions.

SUBJECT KNOWLEDGE CASE STUDY

Capturing Our Coast (CoCoast) was a 3-year long citizen science project, funded by the Heritage Lottery Fund. The project was based on a pilot study conducted in Newcastle, UK, which was then expanded to 7 hubs, scattered in different regions of the UK. Across the course of the project, CoCoast trained nearly 3,000 citizen scientists to survey rocky shores, gathering data on marine species to create a wider understanding of UK coastal biodiversity.

Project URL - www.capturingourcoast.co.uk

CoCoast employed Train the Trainer to equip facilitators with the knowledge and skills to train participants, broadening the scientific understanding of the participants and the geographical scope of the project. Information provided to facilitators included -

- Habitats of your location's coastline, including regional geology and coastal formations
- Conservation protection designation
- Coastal ecology
- Tides (spring and neap)
- Environmental stressors
- Temperature, drying out, salinity
- Zonation and shore heights, including how to estimate shore heights
- Wave crash and exposure
- What are you looking for?
- The species – what are you surveying and why – Including common species or rare species, shifting species, invasive species and a species catalogue

LEARNING CONTENT - DATA COLLECTION

Begin with a background to the survey, explaining the reasoning for the technique employed – is it the most robust, is it easy, is it the least time consuming? If facilitators and participants have the freedom to choose their sample site, explain why. Justifying the strategy will help to solidify the scientific process.

Begin with a background to the survey, explaining the reasoning for the technique employed – is it the most robust, is it easy, is it the least time consuming? If facilitators and participants have the freedom to choose their sample site, explain why. Justifying the strategy will help to solidify the scientific process.

Explain the survey – what will it involve, how is it done? Assign your facilitators their sample locations or explain how to select a location and time. The sampling strategy should have a clear and consistent protocol that everyone can refer to, allowing everybody to collect data in a consistent method. Explain what, how and when to record. Run through the equipment that they will be using, explaining what it is and why and how you use it. Show facilitators the data sheet or the website that data is submitted to. Run through this point by point, addressing questions or concerns and explaining key terminology.

Clarify the safety protocol. Detailed safety guidelines should be provided to all facilitators, and they should be guided through them. It is critical that health and safety measures are considered and abided by. Partners should conduct a risk assessment that outline the potential risks when collecting data. You may wish to ask facilitators to sign a waiver detailing that they have read and understood the safety protocol.

Conduct a practise run of the technique with facilitators, clarifying the data collection method. This will offer them an opportunity to test the method, asking any questions they have and addressing any concerns about the technique. Testing the methodology will provide confidence and experience improving their understanding and ability to sufficiently pass on their knowledge.

Critically, facilitators should have a clear understanding of standardisation, validation and quality assurance protocols. Ensuring rigorous and accurate data is important, particularly in citizen science where data quality is already questioned. You should clearly outline practises that control data quality and ensure the most accurate results are gathered. consistency in the training of facilitators will ensure they all receive the same messages, and reduce the chance of misinterpretation. Data should only be collected by those who have undergone the necessary training.

LEARNING CONTENT – FACILITATION SKILLS

Offer opportunities for the group to practise presenting, allowing time for feedback. Highlight the importance of body language, tone and pitch of voice and discuss the best way to design presentations to maintain interest. Encourage your facilitators to speak confidently and clearly. Messages should be clear and concise, focusing on the core message and outcomes of the training.

Allow plenty of time to cover the content and ample opportunities for reflection and questions. Quick probing actions, such as asking for thumbs up and thumbs down to signify confidence, is a good idea for assessing the general feelings of the group. You should summarise large blocks of information to reinforce the learning – you could do this yourself or ask members of the group to recap, encouraging information retention through repetition.

It is important not to assume a certain level of knowledge. Knowing your audience will allow you to assess the understanding, but do not be dismissive and assume what is understood prior to the training. Although something may be clear to the project team, you should still explain topics that have scientific consensus. Explain concepts succinctly and with enough depth to match the understanding needed for the training, avoiding phrases such as ‘obviously you’ve heard of...’ or ‘I’m sure you already understand...’, which could alienate facilitators and reduce their confidence.

Pose questions to the group. When conducted in a welcoming and inclusive way, questioning can facilitate interaction and promote confidence through making valid points or contributions. Avoid posing difficult or overly complex questions that most will not know the answer to. If you get an answer other than the one you are looking for, identify what is relevant about that response; you should welcome ideas from the group, promoting an open discussion space, in which participants are encouraged to contribute. It can be helpful to specify time for this, as inviting ideas at any point could derail conversations and interrupt the flow of the session.

Working with diverse groups presents opportunities and challenges. You can benefit from the breadth of knowledge that facilitators bring, spurring excellent discussion and sharing of ideas. However, occasionally people can have strong opinions or ideas that may not align with those of the project or others. It is important to remain patient, expressing your appreciation for their passion and enthusiasm whilst handling the issue as tactfully as possible. Ways to avoid such challenges include establishing ways of working in collaboration with your group. Creating a 'contract' that is devised together increases the likelihood of accountability to the prescribed working style, as it was established in agreement. You could establish a shared responsibility for the success of the training, a mutual obligation to respect and consider the values and opinions of others or specific methods of allowing others to ask questions.

You may wish to conduct a session about learning styles. An understanding of learning styles could assist facilitators in pitching the content at the correct level and in the correct channels, which could improve engagement and understanding. You can also increase engagement by ensuring the content is up-to-date and accessible and ensuring you establish a connection with the group, allowing for involvement and discussion.

Facilitators should be taught the importance of listening. Establishing ways of working to ensure all participants feel welcome to contribute is crucial. Asking open ended questions, asking for clarification or expanding on a point, or even just acknowledging the contribution made can establish positive working relationships. Additionally, listening allows facilitators to establish the knowledge base of the group, understand concerns participants may have and feedback information to the project teams. It is similarly crucial that these ways of working and listening skills are unilateral among the project team, in order to support facilitators and encourage them to share their understanding and feedback.

LEARNING CONTENT – PARTICIPANT MANAGEMENT

Participant management is a crucial part of a facilitators training, particularly if they are the point of contact. Facilitators should understand the volunteer journey, detailing the interaction that volunteers have with the project or activity. This includes how to sign-up volunteers, the level of contact to maintain, maintain enjoyment within the project, the end of their journey and recognising achievement and contribution. A critical aspect of this includes recruitment. It should be made clear whether the project partners or the facilitators will be responsible for recruiting, and the process should be clear. Questions to consider are – Will you use an external organisation to recruit? How will you advertise the opportunity? Will you interview potential volunteers? How many volunteers should they aim to recruit? What are the official processes for signing up a volunteer?

It is critical to remain in contact with facilitators and participants. A communications plan should be established and the channels by which to communicate detailed. Facilitators should know how and when to contact volunteers, if it is their responsibility to do so. Providing drafts or templates of emails and social media posts is a good foundation for volunteers, allowing them to understand the language and messages you wish to utilise.

Team building skills equip facilitators to get the best from volunteers and understand more about the dynamics of diverse groups. Team building strategies establish the partnership and enforces the collective and collaborative nature of the task. Activities can be used to establish a welcoming and safe environment, helping facilitators and participants to become acquainted. This could begin with an exercise in which participants detail why they chose to get involved and what they want to gain from the training. Alternatively, you could define a list of characteristics and ask participants to find different people in the room with those characteristics. There are a broad range of ideas for team building exercises, that vary in length and complexity.

All of the above aspects will play a role in retention of volunteers. Drop-outs can be unavoidable, but mechanisms can be employed to increase volunteer retention and prepare for suspended engagement. This includes establishing reliable channels of communication, making volunteers and facilitators aware of the support networks in place for them, offering other opportunities to participate based on interest and acknowledging and celebrating the contribution they have.

Legal and ethical considerations are also a large component of participant management and must be considered extensively. Health and Safety procedures must be clear, valid and stringent – project partners should ensure all facilitators are aware of and abide by the procedures, and ensure that their volunteers do the same. Relevant data regulations, such as GDPR, should be abided by and facilitators and participants should understand how they are relevant to the work they are doing and how to avoid breaching them. You may wish to provide proforma templates for legal and ethical considerations to your facilitators. All of the above should also be considered by project partners in regards to facilitators.

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Once training is conducted, explain what's next for your facilitators. This could include collecting kit, being allocated in to pairs, being allocated a data site, deadlines for surveillance and data submission, support and engagement and contact details. You should also conduct a review of the training day, clarifying important details and allowing facilitators to provide feedback. Ensure you maintain contact with your facilitators, supporting them where necessary, and acknowledge the effort and contribution they have made.

When conducted well, Train the Trainer can be a valuable addition to a citizen science project, promoting multilateral ways of working and increasing the confidence and knowledge of participants. It is important to recognise the commitment to training of this nature, whilst highlighting the benefits. Ensure protocols are considered extensively and fit the brief of the project.

This resource aims to support citizen scientists in conducting a Train the Trainer workshop. It will form part of a repository for citizen science resources, hosted on the EU-Citizen.Science platform. The platform will be a repository for a range of resources – guidelines, best practice recommendations, tools and other materials – that cover different aspects of citizen science. By making these available in one place, the platform will build a virtual library for citizen science in Europe. For training, networks and guidance, please visit the EU-Citizen.Science website.

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